

Dual Use Applications of Wright Laboratory Avionics Technologies to Computer Assisted Minimally Invasive Surgery (CAMIS)

Maj. Robert Williams, USAF

Wright Laboratory Avionics Directorate
Target Recognition Technology Branch, Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio 45433

ABSTRACT - Wright Laboratory Avionics Directorate is helping to assemble a team of defense and civilian researchers to transition defense avionics and related technologies to the medical community with the goal of improving the Computer Assisted Minimally Invasive Surgery (CAMIS) concept. Key partners include Ohio Aerospace Institute (OAI), a not for profit state chartered agency, Cleveland Clinic Foundation hospital, and Picker International, medical equipment manufacturer. The CAMIS concept is in response to the fact that despite technical advances, most excision surgeries are exploratory rather than remedial. As a result, large incisions are required so the surgeon can first search for the "target" tissue and then, more cutting is needed to remove or destroy the "target". CAMIS is an opportunity to transition defense avionics technologies to help tackle a critical non-defense issue on the national agenda, health care.

I. Background

The Wright Laboratory Avionics Directorate, based at Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, executes a broad-based technology program that includes navigation, surveillance, reconnaissance, system architecture, electronic warfare, fire control, communications, system architecture, signal processing, and software. The Mission Avionics Division supports the directorate's mission as the Air Force's center of excellence for leading edge avionics technologies which find, identify, and destroy enemy targets, anywhere, anytime, any weather.

In recognition of the breadth and depth of the directorate's technology program, developers of the Computer Assisted Minimally Invasive Surgery (CAMIS) concept are working closely with the directorate to explore opportunities for transitioning appropriate defense technologies to this critical area in health care. In some dual use areas, as much as a 5 year technology gap exists according to medical researchers.

II. Origin of CAMIS

In 1989, the Cleveland Clinic Foundation (CCF) Department of Neurosurgery established the Center for Computer Assisted Neurosurgery to develop a system which would generate computer-enhanced three-dimensional images in real time during surgery so that the surgeon can "see"

contrasts between malignancies and normal tissue and the irregular outline of lesions more accurately than is possible with the naked eye. CCF joined forces with Picker International (PI) in 1991 to develop a prototype system which consists of a locating device, and appropriate software, hardware and display units. The locating device or wand senses data about the internal area toward which it is pointed, transmits these data to a cart based super computer where specially designed software interprets image data and generates a 3-D enhanced image on a monitor in real time for the surgeon.

The Computer Assisted Minimally Invasive Surgery (CAMIS) concept is in response to the fact that despite recent technical advances in the field of medical imaging, most surgeons' advanced intelligence about 3-D lesions is still obtained from 2-D images, making most excision surgeries exploratory rather than remedial. Since organs and soft tissue move and deform as the patient changes position, breathes or is manipulated during the operating procedure, typical pre-operative images yield pictures which differ significantly from what the surgeon actually sees once inside. As a result, larger-than ideal incisions are required so the surgeon can "find" the tumor and then, even more cutting

is necessary to ensure that all of the malignant tissue is removed.

In 1993, in close collaboration with Ohio Aerospace Institute (OAI), a not for profit state chartered agency, Wright Laboratory Avionics Directorate identified the CAMIS concept as a dual use candidate. A close study of the concept identified several technical challenges suitable for possible dual use collaboration.

III. Technical Challenges

The following areas have been identified as candidates for improvement through appropriate transitioning of defense avionics and related technologies:

1. Localizer wand
2. Computer hardware
3. Information display
4. System architecture
5. Man-machine interface

The current localizer wand generates broad band ultrasonic signals which a detector array processes to determine the signal location in referenced 3-D space.

In doing so, the CAMIS computer can associate the location of the wand with specific pre-stored medical images. The current wand is cumbersome to use and sensitive to background noise which can cause the detector array to "lose track." The surgeon would like the wand to be redesigned for easier and more robust operation in a harsh surgical environment.

The computer hardware currently processes a single imaging modality (typically magnetic resonance or MR). Research indicates that improved detection and recognition of target phenomena can be realized through proper multi-modality processing, i.e. sensor fusion. In addition to improved information extraction algorithms, there is a need for faster algorithms. The hardware cost must be small to make it a commercially viable system.

Another area for possible improvement is the result of the surgeon having to look away from the target region to monitor mission progress as displayed on a high resolution computer display. Attention must then be turned back to the patient requiring that the surgeon remember what was displayed and mentally correlate that computer visual information to the actual surgical operation. A helmet mounted display (HMD) could possibly allow the surgeon to remain on task at all times.

Using the IBM PC as an example, the ability to re configure a baseline CAMIS system using competitor's subsystems to create custom solutions to custom applications would revolutionize health care technology and potentially drive technology cost down. This however will not be possible without a method for standardizing and integrating across all modalities and interfaces; both hardware and software.

Finally, the surgeon currently interacts with the CAMIS system through computer control

panels located near the computer display. This forces the surgeon to look away from the target region momentarily. Voice-controlled interaction with the information display would free the surgeon to concentrate on the task.

IV. Dual Use Collaboration

The fullest potential of CAMIS will be more quickly realized through a strategic alliance between the medical practitioners and researchers of CCF and medical instrument manufacturer of PI with the technical expertise of additional medical practitioners and researchers from:

1. Wright Laboratory
2. Armstrong Laboratory
3. Air Force Institute of Technology
4. Loral Defense Systems
5. Wright Patterson Medical Center
6. Wilford Hall Medical Center
7. NASA
8. Ohio State University
9. University of Cincinnati
10. Central State University

The Air Force elements will bring avionics, automatic target recognition, helmet mounted display, and image processing research

capabilities to the team. The two Air Force hospitals are expected to provide a military health care perspective to the development process while Loral Defense Systems has decades of sensor processing expertise which could be applied to CAMIS as a defense conversion opportunity. NASA has also expressed interest in participating in the area of data transmission. The team is completed with the inclusion of academic research expertise found in the three Ohio universities.

V. Expected Results

Preliminary results indicate at least a 30 percent reduction in average length of stay using CAMIS. Based on the national average of 10 million surgical operations per year requiring hospital stays of at least one day (at a cost of approximately \$1,000 per day), at least 3 billion dollars could be saved per year. If the average stay is 4 days, the savings would be 12 billion dollars.

Technology "spin off" and "spin on" are direct beneficiaries of any future CAMIS participation. Medical researchers agree on the many advancements made in the defense technologies that have potential for "spinning off" to medical applications.

Similarly, it is reasonable to assume that further technical advancements made in the medical community with the aid of "spin off" technologies may potentially "spin back onto" the defense community later, thus providing possible fresh new insight into tough defense research problems.

VI. Conclusion

The current national interest in dual use has created opportunities to pursue non traditional partnerships which have the potential for achieving tremendous success. As the CAMIS effort has shown, dual use collaboration is possible and can potentially benefit all parties involved. Such opportunities, however, will not be possible without the support of management.

